

VVER-440 Full Core Benchmark Solutions with DYN3D

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ABSTRACT

For verification and validation of lattice code and core models for the VVER-440 reactor type, HZDR and Framatome have analyzed the VVER-440 Full Core Benchmark [1], [2] with the DYN3D nodal core simulator. The transport codes Serpent (HZDR) and HELIOS (Framatome) were used to generate two-group data. A full-core Serpent model serves as reference. The DYN3D results show good agreement with each other and the reference in the unrodded and rodded benchmark cases.

Keywords: VVER-440, HELIOS, Serpent, DYN3D

1. INTRODUCTION

As a continuation of the work on verification and validation (V&V) of VVER-1000 lattice and core simulator models [4], [5], the present paper shows a similar study for the VVER-440 reactor.

A particularity of the VVER-440 core is that there are two types of fuel assemblies: The fixed fuel assemblies, and the follower fuel assemblies which are axially connected to control assemblies. The control assemblies displace the follower fuel for power maneuvering and reactivity control.

The paper is structured as follows. Chapter 2 introduces the VVER-440 Full-Core 2D benchmark in the unrodded and rodded state, Chapter 3 presents HELIOS and Serpent lattice code models of fuel and control assemblies as well as the radial reflector. These models are used to generate two-group cross-sections for the nodal core simulator DYN3D. Chapter 4 shows results for eigenvalue, assembly and pin powers by DYN3D using HELIOS and Serpent cross-sections in comparison with Serpent reference results. Chapter 5 gives brief conclusions.

2. THE VVER-440 FULL-CORE BENCHMARK

The VVER-440 Full-Core Benchmark describes a 2D section of a VVER-440 fresh core in unrodded [1] and rodded state [2].

Figure 1 shows the core loading, where the positions marked with bold edges are the ones which contain the absorber in the rodded state. The right part of the figure shows the layout of the assembly with average enrichment 4.25 w/o U-235, where the fuel pins are marked with their individual enrichment and the fuel pins 4G contain 3.35 w/o Gd₂O₃. The assembly types 1.6 and 2.4 contain only fuel pins of enrichments 1.6 w/o and 2.4 w/o, respectively. For this paper, geometrical and material data were taken from the references [1], [2]. In [1], the fuel composition is split up into individual nuclide densities. Other composition information is given in element fractions which, for this study, were decomposed into individual nuclides. The coolant is borated water (3.0 g/kg) at a density of 0.777537 g/cm³. All temperatures are 543.15K.

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Figure 1: Core positions and loading (left) and fuel assembly layout of type 4.25 w/o U-235.

3. MODELS AND METHODS

3.1. Reference Calculation

To be consistent in nuclear data, a reference Monte Carlo model was set up in Serpent [3], using the ENDF/B-VII.1 evaluated nuclear data library. Figure 2 visualizes the model for the unrodded and rodded case. The yellow lines indicate the 60° sector for which the results are displayed in Chapter 4. Power distributions were produced with an assumption of full fission energy deposition in the fission site, e.g. without accounting for gamma-smearing effect.

Figure 2: Serpent reference models for unrodded (left) and rodded case. The yellow lines indicate a 60° sector.

3.2. Two-group Data Generation with HELIOS

HELIOS [7], version 2.04.02 was applied, using the 58-group ENDF/B-VII.1 library and the Method of Characteristics (MOC) solver.

Similar to [4], [5] the fuel assemblies were modeled in 60° symmetry with periodic boundary conditions in the assembly interior and reflective on the outer edges, see Figure 3 (left). By homogenization, two-group macroscopic cross-sections (XS) are produced. Assembly discontinuity factors (ADF) are

evaluated for the outer boundary, and pin-form factors according to the normalized 1-group kappa-fission cross-section.

Figure 3: HELIOS models of 4.25 w/o fuel assembly (left), radial reflector R1 (middle), and control assembly.

The seven symmetrically different regions of the radial reflector are modeled in individual 7-assembly-size models R1-R7 with their actual neighboring driver fuels and neighboring inert regions, see Figure 3 (middle). Two-group macroscopic XS are extracted by homogenization from the central region. Reflector discontinuity factors are calculated by the method [10], i.e., an analytic solution of the two-group diffusion equation on the reflector region with the incoming and outgoing neutron currents j_{in} and j_{out} as boundary conditions.

The control assembly model is shown in Figure 3 (right). The inert part is $1/12^{\text{th}}$ of the control absorber, the active part composed of $1/2$ and $1/6^{\text{th}}$ fuel assembly 1.6 w/o. The model involves reflective boundary conditions on all outer surfaces. Discontinuity factors for the control assembly are determined by the same method as for the radial reflector.

3.3. Few-group Data Generation with Serpent

The second set of homogenized few-group data is produced using Serpent 2.2.1 with the ENDF/B-VII.1 library. Fuel assembly properties (XS, pin-power form factors and discontinuity factors) are obtained from 2D infinite-lattice models with periodic boundary conditions, illustrated in Figure 4 (left). To emulate the spectral conditions of an assembly embedded in a core, Serpent's fundamental-mode critical spectrum correction is applied.

Figure 4: Serpent model models of the 4.25 w/o fuel assembly (left), control assembly supercell (middle), cut from the radial reflector model (right).

Control-assembly XS are computed using a dedicated 2D infinite supercell configuration, where the absorber cell is surrounded by fuel assemblies as depicted in Figure 4 (middle).

Radial reflector XS are obtained from a 2D full-core Serpent model that is identical to the one used for the benchmark reference solution. 30-degree symmetry of the reflector results in seven unique fuel-assembly-size reflector cells. The reflector zoning used for homogenization is shown in Figure 4 (right).

DYN3D XS-libraries are condensed to 2 energy groups. Discontinuity factors for fuel assemblies are evaluated as a ratio between side-averaged and volume-averaged heterogeneous scalar fluxes. Discontinuity factors for reflector cells and control assemblies are evaluated as a ratio between side-averaged heterogeneous and homogeneous fluxes. For the 2-group case, the homogeneous fluxes are computed using Serpent’s internal diffusion solver.

3.4. DYN3D Model

The Multi-Group (MG) version of DYN3D [8], [9] was used for the simulations both with HELIOS and Serpent-generated XS. The HEXNEM3 [11] solver, based on hexagonal nodes, was applied. The core is modelled in full symmetry (349 fuel assemblies) with one ring of radial reflectors around, forming a total of 421 hexagonal nodes in a single axial layer. Axially, the boundary conditions are reflective; radially, different boundary conditions are used for HELIOS and Serpent XS due to the difference in discontinuity factor methodology: black boundary conditions with HELIOS XS, whereas an albedo of 0.56 for the fast and of 0.92 for the thermal energy group was applied with Serpent XS. The values were obtained the Serpent radial reflector model as ratio between incoming and outgoing partial currents on the jagged surface formed by the outer faces of the radial reflector regions, see Figure 4, right. Fixed thermal-hydraulic feedback conditions were prescribed, and eigenvalue-search calculations performed.

4. RESULTS

Table I shows the eigenvalues obtained by the Serpent reference and DYN3D calculations as well as their differences. DYN3D(H) denotes results by DYN3D using the HELIOS-generated library, and DYN3D(S) using the Serpent-generated library.

Table I: Eigenvalues comparison.

Configuration	Reference	DYN3D(H)	$\Delta\rho_{D(H)-S}$ (pcm)	DYN3D(S)	$\Delta\rho_{D(S)-S}$ (pcm)
unrodded	1.08840	1.08735	-89	1.08844	3
rodded	1.06466	1.06346	-106	1.06424	-37

4.1. Assembly Power Distribution

Fuel Assembly (FA) powers from the reference calculation were averaged over all symmetric positions in the core. All calculation results were normalized such that the sum of all assembly powers is 349 in the unrodded and 342 in the rodded configuration. Table II gives a statistical overview of the assembly normalized power differences DYN3D – Reference (10^{-2}).

Table II: Statistics of assembly power differences (10^{-2}).

	Unrodded		rodded	
	DYN3D(H)	DYN3D(S)	DYN3D(H)	DYN3D(S)
MIN	-0.7	-1.1	-0.9	-1.2
MAX	0.4	0.8	0.9	1.2
RMS	0.3	0.4	0.4	0.5

Figure 5 shows the relative assembly powers calculated by DYN3D(H) and the Serpent reference together with their absolute difference (10^{-2}). The color coding is according to the difference and the same for both the unrodded (left) and rodded case. Figure 6 shows the analogue comparison of DYN3D(S) with Serpent.

Figure 5: FA powers: DYN3D(H) (top), Reference (middle), D(H)-R (bottom) for the unrodded and rodded case.

Figure 6: FA powers DYN3D(S) (top), Reference (middle), D(S)-R (bottom) for the unrodded and rodded case.

4.2. Pin Power Distribution

Like the assembly powers, for the reference calculation, the fuel pin powers were averaged over all symmetrical positions. All calculation results were normalized such that the sum of all fuel pin powers is $349 \times 126 = 43974$ in the unrodded and $342 \times 126 = 43092$ in the rodded case.

Table III: Statistics of pin power differences (10-2).

	unrodded		rodded	
	DYN3D(H)	DYN3D(S)	DYN3D(H)	DYN3D(S)
MIN	-6.7	-7.6	-6.8	-8.0
MAX	5.5	3.9	6.0	4.1
RMS	0.8	0.9	1.0	1.0

Figure 7: Serpent reference pin power distribution in rodDED and unrodDED cases.

Figure 8: DYN3D(S) – Reference pin power difference for rodDED and unrodDED case.

Figure 9: DYN3D(H) – Reference pin power difference for rodDED and unrodDED case.

Figure 10: Pin powers and differences to reference – assembly FA#26 with maximum and minimum differences. Top unrodded, bottom rodded.

The results of the Serpent pin power distribution and the differences between DYN3D and Serpent are displayed in Figures 7-10 and statistically evaluated in Table III.

In both rodded and unrodded cases, the maximum and minimum deviation of the pin powers from the reference occur in the fuel assembly #26. The maximum overestimation is reached in Gd pins with relative power about 0.4, while the underestimation is in corner pins with relative power about 1.6. Evidently, such extreme gradient is challenging for DYN3D pin power reconstruction method. As can be seen in Figures 7-10, the pin power errors are concentrated near Gd pins and in corners of outer assemblies, with RMS error around 1×10^{-2} . The errors at the peak power pins are below 2×10^{-2} .

5. CONCLUSIONS

HELIOS and Serpent transport code models have been used for the few-group data creation for the core simulator DYN3D. The DYN3D results have been compared with reference calculation results. With both sets of few-group data, DYN3D(H) and DYN3D(S), accurately reproduce the reference results.

The differences in reactivity are well below 150 pcm from the reference, where best agreement has been achieved with DYN3D(S). The normalized assembly power differences from the reference range between -1.2 and $+1.3 \times 10^{-2}$ with an RMS difference of below 0.5×10^{-2} . This can be considered an excellent agreement. No radial tilt is observed. The normalized pin power differences from the reference range between -8.0 and $+6.0 \times 10^{-2}$ with an RMS difference around 1.0×10^{-2} . In summary the agreement is satisfying for both DYN3D(H) and DYN3D(S).

In future, an extension of the full-core benchmark to 3D and the simulation of a rod-ejection like [6] are foreseen.

REFERENCES

- [1] V. Krýsl, P. Mikoláš, D. Sprinzl, J. Švarný. "Full-Core' VVER-440 Pin Power Calculation Benchmark." In *AER Symposium 2011*, Dresden, Germany, 2011.
- [2] J. Vimpel, V Krýsl, P. Mikoláš, D. Sprinzl, J. Švarný , J. Závorka, I. Panka, I. Pócs, R. Vočka, A. I. Shcherenko and K. Y. Kurakin. "'Full-Core" VVER-440 extended calculation benchmark." *Kerntechnik*, **83**, pp. 282--293 (2018).
- [3] J. Leppänen, V. Valtavirta, A. Rintala, R. Tuominen. "Status of Serpent Monte Carlo code in 2024." *EPJ Nuclear Sciences & Technologies*, **11**, 3 (2025). URL <https://doi.org/10.1051/epjn/2024031>.
- [4] M. Zilly. "X2 VVER-1000 Benchmark Fresh Core Analysis with HELIOS / DYN3D." In *Physor 2022*, Pittsburgh, Pennsylvania, USA, 2022.
- [5] M. Zilly, V. Jauregui Chavez. "V&V of VVER-1000 Core Simulations at Framatome." In *M&C 2023*, Niagara Falls, Ontario, Canada, 2023.
- [6] Y. Bilodid, M. Fischer, M. Zilly, A. Aures, R. Henry, R. Kilger, S. Kliem. "Extension of the X2 VVER-1000 benchmark by a control rod cluster ejection exercise." *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **192**, 110007 (2023). URL <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anucene.2023.110007>.
- [7] C.A. Wemple, H-N.M. Gheorghiu, R.J.J. Stamm'ler, E.A. Villarino. "Recent Advances in the HELIOS-2 Lattice Physics code," In *Physor 2008*, Interlaken, Switzerland, 2008.
- [8] U. Rohde, S. Kliem, U. Grundmann, S. Baier, Y. Bilodid, S. Duerigen, E. Fridman, A. Gommlich, A. Grahn, L. Holt, Y. Kozmenkov, S. Mittag. "The Reactor Dynamics Code DYN3D – Models, Validation and Applications." *Progress in Nucl. Energy*, **89**, 170 (2016). URL <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pnucene.2016.02.013>.
- [9] S. Kliem, Y. Bilodid, E. Fridman, S. Baier, A. Grahn, A. Gommlich, E. Nikitin, U. Rohde. "The Reactor Dynamics Code DYN3D." *Kerntechnik*, **81**, 170 (2016). URL <https://doi.org/10.3139/124.110692>.
- [10] S. Mittag, P. Petkov, U. Grundmann. "Discontinuity Factors for Non-Multiplying Material In Two-Dimensional Hexagonal Reactor Geometry." *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **30**, 1347 (2003). URL [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0306-4549\(03\)00070-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0306-4549(03)00070-7).
- [11] Y. Bilodid, U. Grundmann, S. Kliem. "The HEXNEM3 nodal flux expansion method for the hexagonal geometry in the code DYN3D." *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **116**, pp. 187-194 (2008). URL <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anucene.2018.02.037>.